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URGANCH SHAHAR AHOLI ZICHLIGINING ANIQLASHNING ILMIIY ASOSLARI

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Mazkur maqolada 2025-yil 1-yanvar holatiga ko'ra Urganch shahrida mavjud 40 ta mahalla fuqarolar yig'inlari kesimida aholi soni va hudud maydonlariga oid ma'lumotlar tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi aholi zichligini aniqlash va shahar hududlarining fazoviy rivojlanish xususiyatlarini baholashdan iborat. Har bir mahalla bo'yicha aholi zichligi kishi/km² ko'rinishida hisoblanib, geografik axborot tizimlari (GIS) dasturi yordamida aholi zichligi kartogrammasi ishlab chiqildi. Olingan natijalar asosida shaharning yuqori va past zichlikka ega hududlari aniqlanib, ularning ijtimoiy infratuzilma va xizmat ko'rsatish majmualari bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasi shaharsozlik nuqtai nazaridan tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot natijalari hududlarni rejalashtirish va shahar rivojini optimallashtirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi

В данной статье проанализированы данные о численности населения и площади территорий 40 махаллинских сходов граждан города Ургенч по состоянию на 1 января 2025 года. Основной целью исследования является определение плотности населения и оценка пространственных особенностей развития городских территорий. Плотность населения по каждой махалле была рассчитана в показателях чел./км², а полученные данные обработаны с использованием геоинформационных систем (ГИС), на основе которых разработана картограмма плотности населения. На основе результатов исследования были выявлены зоны с высокой и низкой плотностью населения, а также проведён градостроительный анализ уровня обеспеченности данных территорий объектами социальной инфраструктуры и сервисного обслуживания. Результаты исследования имеют важное значение для территориального планирования и оптимизации развития городской среды.

This article analyzes data on population size and territorial area of 40 mahalla citizens' assemblies in Urgench city as of January 1, 2025. The main objective of the study is to determine population density and assess the spatial development characteristics of urban areas. Population density for each mahalla was calculated in persons per square kilometer (persons/km²), and the obtained data were processed using Geographic Information Systems (GIS), resulting in the development of a population density cartogram. Based on the analysis, areas with high and low population density were identified, and an urban planning assessment of the availability of social infrastructure and service facilities within these zones was conducted. The research findings are of significant importance for territorial planning and optimization of urban development.

Kalit so'zlar: Aholining zichligi, geoaxborot tizimlari (GIS), kartogramma, fazoviy tahlil, mahalla fuqarolar yig'ini, hududiy rejalashtirish, ijtimoiy infratuzilma, urbanizatsiya.

Ключевые слова: Плотность населения, геоинформационные системы (ГИС), картограмма, пространственный анализ, махаллинский сход граждан, территориальное планирование, социальная инфраструктура, урбанизация.

Keywords: Population density, geographic information systems (GIS), cartogram, spatial analysis, mahalla citizens' assembly, territorial planning, social infrastructure, urbanization.

Kirish. Shaharlarning barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlashda aholi zichligi muhim rejalashtiruvchi omil hisoblanadi. Aholining hududiy joylashuvi shahar infratuzilmasi, transport tizimi, ijtimoiy xizmatlar va ekologik holatga bevosita ta'sir

ko'rsatadi. Ayniqsa, urbanizatsiya jarayonlari jadallashayotgan sharoitda aholi zichligining notekis taqsimlanishi shaharsozlik muammolarini yuzaga keltiradi [1,2].

Urganch shahri Xorazm viloyatining yirik ma'muriy va ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy markazi

bo‘lib, shahar hududida aholining joylashuvi mahallalar kesimida sezilarli farqlanadi. Shu bois aholi zichligini GIS texnologiyalari asosida baholash va fazoviy tahlil qilish shahar hududlarini rejalashtirishda muhim ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyatga ega [3,4].

Mazkur tadqiqotning maqsadi 2025-yil 1-yanvar holatiga Urganch shahridagi 40 ta mahalla fuqarolar yig‘inlari bo‘yicha aholi soni va hudud maydonlari asosida aholi zichligini hisoblash, GIS yordamida kartogramma yaratish va olingan natijalarni

shaharsozlik nuqtai nazaridan tahlil qilishdan iborat [3,4].

Qo‘llanilgan materiallar va usullar

Tadqiqotda Urganch shahrining 40 ta mahalla fuqarolar yig‘inlari bo‘yicha rasmiy demografik ma’lumotlardan foydalanildi. Har bir mahalla uchun aholi soni va hudud maydoni (km²) aniqlandi [3,4].

Urganch shahrida mavjud aholi soni, xonadonlar soni va oilalar soni haqida umumiy ma’lumotlar 1-rasmda keltirilgan.

1-rasm. Urganch shahridagi mavjud MFY lardagi aholi soni ma’lumotlari

Aholi zichligi quyidagi formula asosida hisoblandi:

$$D_i = \frac{N_i}{S_i} \quad (1)$$

bu yerda:

D_i - i-mahallaning aholi zichligi (kishi/km²),

N_i -i-mahalladagi aholi soni (kishi),

S_i -i-mahallaning hudud maydoni (km²).

Hisoblangan natijalar ArcGIS/QGIS dasturiga kiritilib, mahallalar bo‘yicha aholi zichligi kartogrammasi ishlab chiqildi. Fazoviy tahlil usuli yordamida aholi zichligining hududiy taqsimlanish qonuniyatlari aniqlandi.

Natijalar

Hisob-kitoblar shuni ko‘rsatdiki, Urganch shahrida aholi zichligi mahallalar kesimida keskin farqlanadi. Masalan, hududi kichik bo‘lib, aholisi ko‘p bo‘lgan markaziy mahallalarda aholi zichligi juda yuqori qiymatlarni tashkil etadi. Aksincha, hududi

katta bo'lgan chekka mahallalarda aholi zichligi pastroq ekanligi aniqlandi.

GIS asosida tuzilgan kartogramma aholining yuqori zich joylashgan hududlari asosan shahar markaziga yaqin, transport aloqalari rivojlangan va ijtimoiy infratuzilma obyektlari ko'p joylashgan mahallalarda jamlanganini ko'rsatdi. Past zichlikdagi hududlar esa yangi rivojlanayotgan va shahar

chekka qismida joylashgan mahallalarga to'g'ri keladi.

Mahallalar aholi zichligiga ko'ra uch guruhga ajratildi: yuqori, o'rta va past zichlikdagi hududlar. Ushbu guruhlash shahar hududlarini funksional rejalashtirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Urganch shahar aholi zichligining kartogrammasi 2-rasmda keltirilgan.

2-rasm. Urganch shahar aholi zichligi kartogrammasi

Muhokama

Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, aholi zichligining yuqori bo'lishi ijtimoiy infratuzilma obyektlariga tushadigan yuklamani oshiradi. Ayniqsa, ta'lim muassasalari, sog'liqni saqlash obyektlari va jamoat transporti xizmatlariga bo'lgan talab yuqori zichlikdagi hududlarda kuchliroq namoyon bo'ladi.

Past zichlikdagi mahallalar esa shaharni istiqbolda kengaytirish, yangi turar joy massivlarini joylashtirish va yashil hududlarni rivojlantirish uchun qulay hududlar sifatida qaralishi mumkin. Shu

nuqtai nazardan, aholi zichligi kartogrammasi shahar bosh rejasini ishlab chiqishda muhim analitik vosita hisoblanadi.

Xulosa

Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, Urganch shahrida aholi zichligining hududiy taqsimlanishi notekis bo'lib, bu holat shaharsozlik rejalashtirishda kompleks va differensial yondashuvni talab etadi. Geoaxborot tizimlaridan foydalanish aholi zichligini aniqlash va baholashda yuqori aniqlik hamda vizual tahlil imkoniyatlarini yaratdi.

Mazkur tadqiqot natijalari Urganch shahrining hududiy rejalashtirish hujjatlarini takomillashtirish, ijtimoiy infratuzilmani joylashtirish va urbanizatsiya jarayonlarini boshqarishda ilmiy asos sifatida xizmat qilishi mumkin.

FOYDALANGAN ADABIYOTLAR

RO‘YXATI

1. ShNQ 2.07.01-23 “Aholi punktlarining hududlarini rivojlantirish va qurishni shaharsozlik jihatidan rejalashtirish”// O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Qurilish va Uy-joy kommunal xo‘jaligi vazirligi // Toshkent, 2023-111 b.
2. Косцов А.В., Бахирев И.А., Боровик Е.Н., Транспортная планировка городов. Учебное пособие. Москва. А-проджект 2017 г.
3. А.А. Qutliyev Tarixiy shaharlarda avtotransport harakatini rejalashtirishda shaharsozlik usullarini takomillashtirish (Xiva shahri misolida) mavzusidagi PhD dissertatsiyasi, 235-bet, T. 2025y.
4. А.А. Qutliyev Shahar hududini urbanizatsiyaga tayyorlash tamoyillari. Uslubiy qo‘llanma. Urganch-2025 yil.

